

Poll: Religious Place (v1.2)

Published on: 26 December 2022

Zaouia Sayyida Mannoubia

By Bou Ali Malika, Zaytouna

Entry tags: Sufi, Religious Group, Tunisia, North Africa, Religious Place, Mysticism

La femme marabout Assayida Al-Mannoubiya est célèbre auprès du grand public, et son Zaouia est visitée par des personnes pour diverses demandes.

Date Range: 1267 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Tunis Gorjani

Region tags: North Africa, Tunisia

En Tunisie, il existe deux Zaouias pour la femme marabout Assayida al-Mannoubia l'une dans la cité de la Mannouba, à l'ouest de Tunis, et l'autre à Gorjani, au sud de Tunis.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Tree, grove, or forest

– Other [specify]: Ce n'est pas haut, et il y avait des champs à côté, mais le lieu de sa sépulture se trouve sur un haut lieu

Reference: "عامر الجريدي". المؤرخ د. عبد الجليل بوقرة: السيدة المنوبية، من ألقها إلى بانها. <http://ameurjeridi.blogspot.com>, n.d. http://ameurjeridi.blogspot.com/2012/10/blog-post_16.html.

Reference: تونس: منشورات كارم. Vol. 1. توفيق عامر بن. Edited by محمّد الكلاوي. مناقب السّيّدة عائشة المنوبيّة. الشريفة, 2011.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes

- ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Burned
 - Notes: Le Maqam a été brûlé par les intégristes en 2012

- ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - For religious reasons
 - Notes: Par des Salafistes après la révolution de 2011

- ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Human-caused accident

- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes

- ↳ In antiquity
 - More than once

- ↳ In modernity
 - Post-Renaissance

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - No

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: الجن: الأرواح

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: 2011 - تونس - محمد الكحلوي، مناقب السيدة عائشة المنوبية، منشورات كارم الشريف. تونس - 2011
- Source 2: 1925 - تونس - العربي، الغربي، كتاب مناقب السيدة عائشة المنوبية، مطبعة النهضة. تونس - 1925
- Source 3: Katia Boissevain, *SAINTE PARMi LES SAINTS Sayyda Mannûbiya ou les recompositions culturelles dans la Tunisie contemporaine*, Institut de recherche sur le Maghreb contemporain, Tunis, 2005. ASIN : B01700119K

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

- ↳ Type of feature
 - Mound
 - Trackway or road-surface

– Plantings

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: [https://www.bibliotheque.nat.tn/BNT/search.aspx?SC=BNTPARTOUT&QUERY=%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D8%A9+%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D9%88%D8%A8%D9%E\(Ld:5_OFFSET_0',Index:6,NBResults:6,PageRange:3,SearchQuery:\(FacetFilter:%7B%22_356%22:%22Livre%22%7D',ForceSearch:t,InitialSearch:f,Page:0,PageRange:3,QueryGuid:d32ec250-c6f9-49e2-8e38-a23fa2188ec1,QueryString:%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D8%A9%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D9%88%D8%A8%D9%standard,SearchGridFieldsShownOnResultsDTO:!,SearchLabel:!,SearchTerms:%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D8%A9%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D9%88%D8%A8%\(Scenario:!,Scope:BNT,Size:!,Source:!,Support:!,UseCompact:!,UseSpellChecking:!\)](https://www.bibliotheque.nat.tn/BNT/search.aspx?SC=BNTPARTOUT&QUERY=%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D8%A9+%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D9%88%D8%A8%D9%E(Ld:5_OFFSET_0',Index:6,NBResults:6,PageRange:3,SearchQuery:(FacetFilter:%7B%22_356%22:%22Livre%22%7D',ForceSearch:t,InitialSearch:f,Page:0,PageRange:3,QueryGuid:d32ec250-c6f9-49e2-8e38-a23fa2188ec1,QueryString:%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D8%A9%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D9%88%D8%A8%D9%standard,SearchGridFieldsShownOnResultsDTO:!,SearchLabel:!,SearchTerms:%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D8%A9%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D9%88%D8%A8%(Scenario:!,Scope:BNT,Size:!,Source:!,Support:!,UseCompact:!,UseSpellChecking:!))
- Source 1 Description: Un livre qui décrit les manaqib de la Sayyida Mannoubia
- Source 2 URL: https://alazmenah.com/?page=show_det&id=6803
- Source 2 Description: Un article sur la Sainte Mannoubia
- Source 3 URL: https://books.google.tn/books/about/%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%86%D8%B3%D8%A7%D8%A1_%D9%81%D9%8A_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B5%D9%8id=v4rmjwEACAAJ&redir_esc=y
- Source 3 Description: A book about good women in the Maghreb

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Illicit

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2012

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: يقوم المعهد الوطني للتراث بصيانة الزاوية

– Official or descriptive name: Entretien et restauration après l'incendie du sanctuaire par les salafistes

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: صيانة دورية

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: المحافظة على النقوش الداخلية

– Official or descriptive name: Les responsables du sanctuaire assurent également l'entretien grâce au produit de la visite

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

c6f9-49e2-8e38-a23fa2188ec1,QueryString:"%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D8%A9%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D9%88%D8%A8%D standard.SearchGridFieldsShownOnResultsDTO!
(,SearchLabel:",SearchTerms:"%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D8%A9%20%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%86%D9%88%D8%A8"
(Scenario:",Scope:BN,Size:In,Source:",Support:",UseCompact:!f),UseSpellChecking:In)))

—Source 1 Description: Un livre qui décrit les manaqib de la Sayyida Mannoubia

—Source 2 URL: https://alazmenah.com/?page=show_det&id=6803

—Source 2 Description: Un article sur la Sainte Mannoubia

—Source 3 URL:

https://books.google.tn/books/about/%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%86%D8%B3%D8%A7%D8%A1_%D9%81%D9%8A_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B5%D9 id=v4rmjwEACAAJ&redir_esc=y

—Source 3 Description: A book about good women in the Maghreb

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

— Yes

Type of excavation:
— Illicit

Years of excavation:
—Year range: 2012

Name of excavation
—Official or descriptive name: يقوم المعهد الوطني للتراث بصيانة الزاوية
—Official or descriptive name: Entretien et restauration après l'incendie du sanctuaire par les salafistes

— Yes

Type of excavation:
— Scientific

Years of excavation:
—Year range: صيانة دورية

Name of excavation
—Official or descriptive name: المحافظة على النفوس الداخلية
—Official or descriptive name: Les responsables du sanctuaire assurent également l'entretien grâce au produit de la visite

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

—Tree, grove, or forest

—Other [specify]: Ce n'est pas haut, et il y avait des champs à côté, mais le lieu de sa sépulture se trouve sur un haut lieu

Reference: "عامر الجريدي. "المؤرخ د.عبد الجليل بوقرة: السيدة المنوبية، من ألقها إلى باتها".
[Http://ameurjeridi.blogspot.com](http://ameurjeridi.blogspot.com), n.d.. http://ameurjeridi.blogspot.com/2012/10/blog-post_16.html.

Reference: تونس: منشورات كارم. Vol. 1. توفيق عامر بن. محقق الكحلوي. مناقب السيدة عائشة المنوبية. التبريف. 2011.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

— Yes

Type of feature
—Mound
—Trackway or road-surface
—Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure
– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Rectangular

↳ One single feature
– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– Yes

↳ A group of features:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Burned
 - Notes: Le Maqam a été brûlé par les intégristes en 2012
 - ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - For religious reasons
 - Notes: Par des Salafistes après la révolution de 2011
 - ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Human-caused accident
- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In antiquity
 - More than once
 - ↳ In modernity
 - Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - No
- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: الجن: الأرواح

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

- ↳ Specify
 - King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

- ↳ Groups:
 - Men
 - Women
 - Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]:
 - No
 - ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: النقوش تتمثل في آيات قرآنية
- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - Yes [specify]: ألوان مختلفة وخاصه اللون الأخضر

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

- ↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
 - No
- ↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
 - No
- ↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
 - I don't know

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

- ↳ Earth
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Sand
 - Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Pavage des salles du sanctuaire avec du marbre et de la glaçure

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Bois, fer et pierre

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– I don't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– Yes

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
–Other [specify]: Pavage des salles du sanctuaire avec du marbre et de la glaçure

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Bois, fer et pierre

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
– Yes

↳ On the outside:
– Yes

↳ On the inside:
– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:
A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted
– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
– No

↳ Are there statues present:
– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:
A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.
– No

- ↳ Are there paintings present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]:
 - No
 - ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: النقوش تتمثل في آيات قرآنية
 - ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - Yes [specify]: ألوان مختلفة وخاصّة اللون الأخضر

Iconography

- Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
 - No

Beliefs and Practices

- Is supernatural monitoring present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Libations:
 - No
 - ↳ Offerings of food:
 - Yes [specify]: Des animaux tels que des moutons et des poulets sont abattus et la nourriture peut être cuite pour être servie aux visiteurs dans le sanctuaire, cherchant les bénédictions de la Sayyida Mannoubia
 - ↳ Animal sacrifice:
 - Yes [specify]: des moutons ,des poulets ,des Coqs, des chèvres , et des vaches
 - ↳ Human sacrifice:
 - No
 - ↳ Sacred objects:
 - No
 - ↳ Daily life objects:
 - Yes [specify]: Des bougies, des files de tissu verts et encens sont placés à l'entour de

Maqam

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: De l'argent est donné aux responsables du sanctuaire, des Zardas زردة
sorte de restauration du grand public

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: Les visiteurs demandent de se guérir, de faciliter le mariage, d'avoir des enfants et
d'argent

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Yes

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– I don't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each
species

– Yes

↳ Species

–Yes [specify]: Quelques animaux de couleurs rares (coq blanc sans taches...), caméléon....

↳ Part
– I don't know

↳ Remains are consumed:
– No

↳ Remains are disposed of:
– No

Notes: Il faut signaler que ces pratiques sont pour une certaine magie (noir ou non noir)

↳ Divination through human communication:
– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:
– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:
– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Oui comme le fait de jeter du plomb bouilli dans l'eau froide (ça s'appelle en dialecte tunisien حمران الخفيف) pour avoir des formes divers et les interprétées pour savoir le future.

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Pour se faciliter la vie, la femme attache un fil vert à un mur ou aux piliers du sanctuaire

Is this place a tomb/burial:
– Yes

Do rituals occur at this place:
Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.
– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: Les adeptes de sayda mannoubia se comptent par milliers, mais ceux qui assistent aux rituels sont au nombre de 400 à 500.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: la Zarda a lieu chaque année en plus des fêtes religieuses

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– Yes

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
– Yes [specify]: Abattage de coqs, poulets, moutons, vaches et taureaux

↳ Are there human sacrifices:
– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– No

↳ Are they sky deity:
– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

Notes: Notes: sayyda mannoubia est considérée comme guérissant la maladie, apportant des moyens de subsistance et de l'argent, et facilitant le mariage

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No

– Yes

Notes: كانت السيدة المنوية تلميذة الولي الصالح ابو سعيد الباجي وأبي الحسن القادلي

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: non

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

↳ In dreams:
– No

↳ In trance possession:
– No

- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - No
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: sayyda mannoubia n'est pas un dieu supérieur suprême

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

- ↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
 - No
- ↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
 - Yes

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - No
- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
 - Yes [specify]: Au milieu de la Place intérieure centrale

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ Incubation
 - No
- ↳ Healing magic
 - Yes
- ↳ Cleansing
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Offerings of models of body parts:
 - No
- ↳ Expiation
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Les visiteurs peuvent boire de l'eau du sanctuaire ou l'emporter chez eux pour exaucer leurs vœux

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Seulement par des uns ou unes et à des conditions bien précises

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Parfois et par des uns ou unes à des conditions bien précises

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: تقام "الزردة" أو "الوعدة" لطلب الأمنيات في مواعيد سنوية مثلا كجمع محصول أو في مناسبات خاصة ويعلن أنه ستقام الزردة قبل أسبوعين

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Only initiates

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Only locals

– Other [specify in comments]

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– I don't know

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 300_400

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Des vêtements ou des couvertures sont placés pour être utilisés dans le sanctuaire ou comme subvention aux pauvres

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Les malades pour chercher la guérison, les pauvres pour chercher de quoi se nourrir, les célibataires pour se marier, les stériles pour avoir des enfants et annuler la magie

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: On y croit beaucoup à ces pratiques qui consistent au dhikr دكر et à toutes prières

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Les esprits humains se concentre essentiellement sur l'esprit du marabout féminin qui est Sayyida Mannoubia

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: C'est un endroit qui est qualifié de "chaud" سخون dans le dialecte tunisien, ce qui veut dire qu'il y a des Jinns et peut être aussi des anges dans cet endroit

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Dans des conditions précises et généralement d'une façon non attendu et arbitraire

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Le mot physiquement n'est pas très précis le sentiment est plus d'ordre spirituel sentimental intuitive

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: L'entretien est assuré par des bénévoles et des ouvriers affectés par le ministère de la Culture à la protection du patrimoine

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Parfois dans la Hadhra حاضرة d'ailleurs le mot Hadhra signifie la présence des êtres surnaturels

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes

- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No

- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Par les voix parfois

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– No

↳ Are they sky deity:
– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)
– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

Notes: Notes: sayyda mannoubia est considérée comme guérissant la maladie, apportant des moyens de subsistance et de l'argent, et facilitant le mariage

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– No
– Yes

Notes: كانت السيدة المنوية تلميذة الولي الصالح ابو سعيد الباجي وأبي الحسن الشاذلي

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Yes

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: non

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– No

↳ In dreams:
– No

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: sayyda mannoubia n'est pas un dieu supérieur suprême

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Seulement par des uns ou unes et à des conditions bien précises

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Parfois et par des uns ou unes à des conditions bien précises

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: On y croit beaucoup à ces pratiques qui consistent au dhikr ذكر et à toutes prières

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Les esprits humains se concentre essentiellement sur l'esprit du marabout féminin qui est Sayyida Mannoubia

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: C'est un endroit qui est qualifié de "chaud" سخون dans le dialecte tunisien, ce qui veut dire qu'il y a des Jinns et peut être aussi des anges dans cet endroit

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Dans des conditions précises et généralement d'une façon non attendu et arbitraire

- ↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Le mot physiquement n'est pas très précis le sentiment est plus d'ordre spirituel sentimental intuitive

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Parfois dans la Hadhra حاضرة d'ailleurs le mot Hadhra signifie la présence des êtres surnaturels

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes

- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No

- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Par les voix parfois

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - Yes

- ↳ Libations:
 - No

- ↳ Offerings of food:
 - Yes [specify]: Des animaux tels que des moutons et des poulets sont abattus et la nourriture peut être cuite pour être servie aux visiteurs dans le sanctuaire, cherchant les bénédictions de la Sayyida Mannoubia

- ↳ Animal sacrifice:

– Yes [specify]: des moutons ,des poulets ,des Coqs, des chèvres , et des vaches

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– No

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: Des bougies, des files de tissu verts et encens sont placés à l'entour de Maqam

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: De l'argent est donné aux responsables du sanctuaire, des Zardas زردة sorte de restauration du grand public

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Les visiteurs demandent de se guérir, de faciliter le mariage, d'avoir des enfants et d'argent

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– No

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: Les adeptes de sayyda mannoubia se comptent par milliers, mais ceux qui assistent aux rituels sont au nombre de 400 à 500.
- ↳ How often do these rituals take place:
 - specify: la Zarda a lieu chaque année en plus des fêtes religieuses
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Yes

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
 - Yes [specify]: Abattage de coqs, poulets, moutons, vaches et taureaux
- ↳ Are there human sacrifices:
 - No
- ↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:
 - No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
 - No
- ↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Des vêtements ou des couvertures sont placés pour être utilisés dans le sanctuaire ou comme subvention aux pauvres

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Les malades pour chercher la guérison, les pauvres pour chercher de quoi se nourrir, les célibataires pour se marier, les stériles pour avoir des enfants et annuler la magie

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: L'entretien est assuré par des bénévoles et des ouvriers affectés par le ministère de la Culture à la protection du patrimoine

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Yes

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– I don't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– No

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Au milieu de la Place intérieure centrale

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: تقام "الزردة" أو "الوعدة" لطلب الأمنيات في مواعيد سنويّة مثلًا كجمع محصول أو في مناسبات خاصّة: ويعلن أنه ستقام الزردة قبل أسبوعين

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

- Only initiates
- Elites
- Non-elites
- Only locals
- Other [specify in comments]

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– I don't know

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 300_400

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– Yes

↳ Species

– Yes [specify]: Quelques animaux de couleurs rares (coq blanc sans taches..), caméléon...

↳ Part

– I don't know

↳ Remains are consumed:

– No

↳ Remains are disposed of:

– No

Notes: Il faux signaler que ces pratique sont pour une certaine magie (noir ou non noir)

↳ Divination through human communication:

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Oui comme le faite de jeter du plomb boulli dans l'eau froide (ça s'appelle en dialecte tunisien (ضربان الحفيف) pour avoir des formes divers et les interprétées pour savoir le future.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Pour se faciliter la vie, la femme attache un fil vert à un mur ou aux piliers du sanctuaire

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

↳ Cleansing

– Field doesn't know

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Les visiteurs peuvent boire de l'eau du sanctuaire ou l'emporter chez eux pour exaucer leurs vœux

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: بالجهة الشرقية للصحن تقع ملحقات الزاوية من مذبح ومطيخ وبنر وغيرها من الغرف لاستقبال الزوار: لطلب بركات السيدة المنوبية

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Les gens du quartier Manouba ont construit un zaouia en l'honneur de sayyda Mannoubia, et elle n'y a pas été enterrée, mais il y a une chambre funéraire dans laquelle se trouve un cercueil symbolique pour elle

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Il y a des inscriptions de textes coraniques et de motifs floraux dans les entrées en bois des chambres et sur le dôme sous lequel était placé le cercueil symbolique de sayyda Monnoubia , reposant sur quatre coquilles d'angle.

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: يتقدم الزاوية رواق محاط بأقبية طويلة محمولة على أعمدة ذات تيجان تفضي لصحن مكشوف

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: بالجهة الشرقية للصحن تقع ملحقات الزاوية من مذبح ومطبخ ونير وغيرها من الغرف لاستقبال

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: Les gens du quartier Manouba ont construit un zaouia en l'honneur de sayyda Mannoubia, et elle n'y a pas été enterrée, mais il y a une chambre funéraire dans laquelle se trouve un cercueil symbolique pour elle

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Il y a des inscriptions de textes coraniques et de motifs floraux dans les entrées en bois des chambres et sur le dôme sous lequel était placé le cercueil symbolique de sayyda Monnoubia , reposant sur quatre coquilles d'angle.

– Yes

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: يتقدم الزاوية رواق محاط بأقبية طولية محمولة على أعمدة ذات تيجان تفضي لصحن

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Tree, grove, or forest, Other [specify]: Ce n'est pas haut, et il y avait des champs à côté, mais le lieu de sa sépulture se trouve sur un haut lieu, من ألفها, "المؤرخ د. عبد الجليل بوقرة: السيدة المنوية، من ألفها، إلى يائها". [Http://ameurjeridi.blogspot.com](http://ameurjeridi.blogspot.com), n.d.. http://ameurjeridi.blogspot.com/2012/10/blog-post_16.html.

Reference: Tree, grove, or forest, Other [specify]: Ce n'est pas haut, et il y avait des champs à côté, mais le lieu de sa sépulture se trouve sur un haut lieu, مناقب السيدة عائشة المنوية، Edited by توفيق عامر بن تونس: منشورات كارم الشريف, 2011. Vol. 1.